

QECANM Project - Data Management Plan

Version 1.0.0

Description

The present Data Management Plan (DMP) concerns the MSCA-PF project Quantum Estimation and Control for Advanced Noisy Metrology (QECANM), grant agreement 101068347.

Brief summary of the project

The project QECANM aims to advance the field quantum metrology, especially in realistic operating conditions. It has three main pillars: i) understanding the ultimate limits of the quantum estimation of multiple parameters simultaneously, either because all of them are of practical interest, or because a full prior characterization of additional system's parameters is not possible; ii) assessing the impact of environmental noise on the quantum probe, in particular beyond the standard assumption of uncorrelated noise; iii) understanding the limits of metrological schemes based on time-continuous measurements, nowadays feasible in many physical systems (e.g. superconducting qubits, optomechanics), which open the possibility to perform measurement-based feedback control on the system. The overarching goal of QECANM is to advance the state of the art in these three areas by connecting these three pillars. This can be achieved by devising new theoretical tools, both analytical and numerical, to assess the ultimate precision limits in novel and physically relevant scenarios. These tools are rooted in quantum estimation theory and quantum control theory and they will provide fundamental benchmarks for the next generation of quantum sensors.

Structure of the DMP

The main purpose of the DMP is to ensure that all the results obtained within the project are reproducible and easily understandable in the future, both by the researcher and collaborators and by other scientists working in the field.

The DMP is divided in three Datasets:

- A Dataset called "Code for numerical calculations" which contains all the code for numerical calculations, written in Julia and Python.
- A Dataset called "Results of numerical calculations" which will collect the most relevant results obtained by means of numerical experiments that will be included in scientific publications.
- A Dataset called "Theoretical results" which contains results obtained by analytical calculations and arguments, including the use of computer algebra software, but without recurring to numerical simulations. This Dataset will include all the information needed to check the validity of the analytical results and reproduce their outcomes. Concretely it includes LaTeX documents (as well as the pdf obtained by compiling) and Wolfram Mathematica notebooks.

Funder

European Commission | | EC

Grant

Quantum Estimation and Control for
Advanced Noisy Metrology/ No
101068347

Researchers

Francesco Albarelli (orcid:0000-0001-5775-168X)

Organizations

SCUOLA NORMALE SUPERIORE

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [QECANM Data Management Plan](#)

Description:

The present Data Management Plan (DMP) concerns the MSCA-PF project Quantum Estimation and Control for Advanced Noisy Metrology (QECANM), grant agreement 101068347.

Brief summary of the project

The project QECANM aims to advance the field quantum metrology, especially in realistic operating conditions. It has three main pillars: i) understanding the ultimate limits of the quantum estimation of multiple parameters simultaneously, either because all of them are of practical interest, or because a full prior characterization of additional system's parameters is not possible; ii) assessing the impact of environmental noise on the quantum probe, in particular beyond the standard assumption of uncorrelated noise; iii) understanding the limits of metrological schemes based on time-continuous measurements, nowadays feasible in many physical systems (e.g. superconducting qubits, optomechanics), which open the possibility to perform measurement-based feedback control on the system. The overarching goal of QECANM is to advance the state of the art in these three areas by connecting these three pillars. This can be achieved by devising new theoretical tools, both analytical and numerical, to assess the ultimate precision limits in novel and physically relevant scenarios. These tools are rooted in quantum estimation theory and quantum control theory and they will provide fundamental benchmarks for the next generation of quantum sensors.

Structure of the DMP

The main purpose of the DMP is to ensure that all the results obtained within the project are reproducible and easily understandable in the future, both by the researcher and his colleagues and by other scientists working in the field.

The DMP is divided in three Datasets

- A Dataset called "Theoretical results" which contains results obtained by analytical calculations and arguments, including the use of computer algebra software, but without recurring to numerical simulations. This Dataset will include all the information needed to check the validity of the analytical results and reproduce their outcomes. Concretely it includes LaTeX documents (as well as the pdf obtained by compiling) and Wolfram Mathematica notebooks.
- A Dataset called "Code for numerical calculations" which contains all the code for numerical calculations, written in Julia and Python.
- A Dataset called "Results of numerical calculations" which will collect the most relevant results obtained by means of numerical experiments that will be included in scientific publications.

Researchers:

Francesco Albarelli (orcid:0000-0001-5775-168X)

Organizations:

SCUOLA NORMALE SUPERIORE

Contact: Francesco Albarelli

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [European Commission](#) | [EC](#)

Grants: [Quantum Estimation and Control for Advanced Noisy Metrology](#) (DOI:[10.3030/101068347](https://doi.org/10.3030/101068347))

Project: [Quantum Estimation and Control for Advanced Noisy Metrology](#)

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Code for numerical calculations

This dataset contains all the code for numerical simulations.

The dataset will eventually include:

- Functions to evaluate the ultimate precision of single and multiple parameter estimation achievable when a quantum emitter is coupled to a field that can be measured continuously.
- Functions to compute the precision of parameter estimation for particular measurement strategies, including when conditional measurements on the state are possible and including the effects of measurement incompatibility when measuring multiple parameters
- Functions to evaluate bounds to the quantities above that are less computationally intensive, even if potentially less informative.

The code is mostly written in Julia, but some parts will rely on Python code too. The code builds upon existing open-source packages, in particular [QuTiP](#), [TNQMetro](#) and [QuantumOptics.jl](#).

All the dependencies are clearly listed, including information on the particular versions of package used during testing and to produce the results in scientific publications, to ensure reproducibility.

Tutorial Jupyter notebooks will also be included, as a useful pedagogical tool to explain how to use the code.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Software

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

The code depends upon existing open source projects, as mentioned in the description. Parts of the code will be developed taking as a starting point and modifying some of the source code of particular functions included in these open source packages.

This is allowed by the open source licences of the packages TNQMetro (MIT license), QuTiP (BSD-3-Clause license) and QuantumOptics.jl (MIT "Expat" License).

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Other

1.1.5 What is its format?

This dataset essentially contains only text files:

- the main source code is contained in simple and commented text files
- the README file and additional documentation are also text files (potentially in Markdown syntax)
- some tutorial Jupyter notebooks are in ipynb format, but this is still a text-based format.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

100 MB at most

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To obtain information

This code will be produced to investigate the main scientific questions of the research project, but it is expected that it will be useful for other researchers too.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The data consists of code written by the researcher, some AI tools (e.g. Github Copilot) may be used to improve the quality and readability of the code. These tools will not be used for major and conceptual parts of the coding work and their use should not affect the licensing.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Researchers

The code could may be useful in the future to researchers working in the same and related areas.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes, this is planned.

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes, it will be made available at the time of publication.

2.2 Datasets

2.2.1 Does the described output use or support any published dataset?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Output identifiers (DOI)
- Researchers identifiers (ORCID)

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

All the relevant metadata is included in the readme file distributed with the code.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

The metadata describes the provenance of the code and the relation to scientific publications.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Other

The metadata will be indexed by search engines because it will be shared publicly on Github and Zenodo.

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes, administrative metadata will be available in Zenodo

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

GitHub

Zenodo

The code will be deposited in one or more designated GitHub repositories.

The final version of the code used in scientific publications will be linked to and stored in Zenodo, obtaining a PID. In particular, Scuola Normale Superiore has a dedicated Zenodo community.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Has an open access content policy
- Assigns PIDs
- Has data security mechanisms in place

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Code for numerical calculations

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

The code will be released as open source together with the related scientific publications.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

It will remain publicly available on GitHub and Zenodo. Currently, Zenodo offers data preservation for [at least 20 years](#).

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

The data will be available as long as Github and Zenodo will be operating.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes, administrative metadata will be available in any case through Zenodo

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

The metadata is the information contained in the readme file, which explains how to use the code.

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

The administrative metadata will remain available through Zenodo.

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes, related items (publications and other datasets) will be qualified using the RelatedItem element of the DataCite Metadata Schema.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

MIT License

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Readme files

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

The code will remain available on GitHub and Zenodo for the foreseeable future.

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

This information is included in the README files.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Not available

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0 Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Indirect cost

There are no direct costs, since the data will be available on Github and Zenodo.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

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The researcher will be in charge of making sure that the code is available on the GitHub repository and that it will be stored in Zenodo once the scientific publication is released as a preprint.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Results of numerical calculations

This dataset will contain the results of the most important numerical calculations of the project.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

The data is the results of the most relevant numerical calculations generated in the course of the project, in particular those needed to support the writing of scientific papers.

The code used to generate this data is in the previous dataset "Code for numerical calculations".

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Simulation

1.1.5 What is its format?

The data will be saved in the Hierarchical Data Format (HDF5).

HDF is an open scientific data format, widely supported by many open source software platforms, since the libraries are available under a BSD-like license for general use.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

a few GBs

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To obtain information

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The data is generated by running code.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Researchers

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes, this is planned.

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes, it will be made available at the time of publication.

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes, it is generated by the code in the dataset "Code for numerical calculations".

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers (DOI)
- Researchers identifiers (ORCID)

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

Descriptive metadata will be provided, linking the data produced with the code used to produce it, as well as the scientific publications in which the data is analyzed and commented.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Other

The dataset will be made available through Zenodo

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

Administrative metadata in Zenodo is harvestable.

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Results of numerical calculations

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

The dataset will be made available together with the preprint of the scientific article, through Zenodo and the Scuola Normale Superiore Zenodo community.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

The code used to generate this dataset is available in the Dataset "Code for numerical calculations", however to simply access the data any software that supports the Hierarchical Data Format HDF5 is enough.

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

It will be openly available via Zenodo.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

No

The metadata is included together with the dataset and not available separately, so it will not be available independently of it.

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes, related items (publications and other datasets) will be qualified using the RelatedItem element of the DataCite Metadata Schema.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Readme files

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

No

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Use of tools for automatic checks

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0 Euro

Storage

Indirect cost

The dataset will be hosted on Zenodo, and made available through the Scuola Normale Superiore community on Zenodo.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

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The researcher will be responsible of making the data available, by uploading it to Zenodo and including the DOI in the relevant scientific publications.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Theoretical results

This dataset contains all the information needed to reproduce the derivations and theoretical results of the research carried out in the context project QECANM.

The dataset will eventually include:

- PDF documents detailing the analytical calculations and derivations
- Mathematica notebooks containing the analytical calculations that are carried out with the software Wolfram Mathematica.

Most of this information will be eventually made available in scientific publications and/or preprints. However, this dataset will be more comprehensive, and more tailored towards the reproducibility of the calculations.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Other

The data contains the analytical calculations and derivations related to the results of the project.

1.1.5 What is its format?

The data format will be PDF files generated by LaTeX and Mathematica notebooks (extension .nb).

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

around 100 MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To obtain information

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Researchers

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes, this is planned.

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes, it will be made available at the time of publication.

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

<https://www.wolfram.com/mathematica/>

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers (DOI)
- Researchers identifiers (ORCID)

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

The dataset includes PDF files and Mathematica notebooks, which will be uploaded on Zenodo to ensure their preservation and thus the administrative metadata will be available through Zenodo.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Other

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

This dataset is mostly for internal use by the researcher, it is not meant to be shared publicly. At the end of the project an assessment on the opportunity to share this dataset and making it open will be made.

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

For the moment, this dataset is not meant to be useful for a wider audience. It is a purely intentional decision, but there are no legal reasons.

In any case, the most relevant information contained in the dataset will be included in publicly available preprints and papers.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

No

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

Administrative metadata will remain available through Zenodo.

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes, related items (publications and other datasets) will be qualified using the RelatedItem element of the DataCite Metadata Schema.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files

- Other

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

No

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Not available

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0 Euro

Storage

Indirect cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

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The researcher will generate the data and make it available.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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